

A LITERARY EXPLORATION OF GARBHINI CHHARDI IN CLASSICAL AYURVEDIC TEXTS – A COMPREHENSIVE REVIEW

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ABSTRACT

Background: Garbhini Chhardi (vomiting in pregnancy) is a common early gestational disorder that can be correlated with the modern concept of hyperemesis gravidarum. Ayurveda provides a holistic understanding of this condition, emphasizing physiological, psychological, and doshic balance. **Aim:** To critically review classical Ayurvedic references on Garbhini Chhardi and correlate them with modern obstetric perspectives for better understanding and management. **Methods:** Literary data were collected from Brihatrayi (Charaka, Sushruta, and Vagbhata), Kashyapa Samhita, Bhavaprakasha, and contemporary Ayurvedic texts. Modern literature was also referred for correlation. The concepts were compared for Nidana (etiology), Lakshana (symptoms), and Chikitsa (management). **Results:** Garbhini Chhardi arises from the vitiation of Vata and Pitta doshas, influenced by Garbha Vridhi and altered Agni. Ayurvedic management emphasizes Vata-Pitta Shamana, Agni Deepana, and Garbha Poshan using

Pathya-Apathya, Draksha, Amalaki, Shatavari, and preparations like Laja Manda. These correlate with modern approaches to manage hyperemesis through rehydration, nutritional

support, and antiemetic therapy. **Conclusion:** The Ayurvedic concept of Garbhini Chhardi offers a safe and comprehensive management approach focusing on dosha equilibrium, maternal nutrition, and fetal safety. Integrating Ayurvedic and modern approaches can enhance maternal health outcomes.

KEYWORDS: Garbhini Chhardi, Hyperemesis Gravidarum, Ayurveda, Vata-Pitta Dushti, Laja Manda, Shatavari.

INTRODUCTION

Pregnancy is a complex physiological process involving significant hormonal and metabolic alterations. Vomiting and nausea are common during early gestation due to changes in hormones such as hCG and estrogen. Ayurveda refers to this condition as Garbhini Chhardi, resulting from Vata and Pitta vitiation affecting Agni and producing upward movement of doshas.

Though mild vomiting is physiological, excessive and persistent vomiting resembles hyperemesis gravidarum in modern medicine, which can lead to dehydration and maternal-fetal complications. Ayurveda provides preventive and curative guidelines through Garbhini Paricharya, emphasizing Ahara (diet), Vihara (lifestyle), and Aushadhi (medications).

MATERIALS AND METHODS

A literary review was conducted using Ayurvedic classical texts (Charaka Samhita, Sushruta Samhita, Ashtanga Hridaya, Kashyapa Samhita, Bhavaprakasha) and modern literature on pregnancy-related emesis. Inclusion criteria focused on Ayurvedic interpretations of Garbhini Chhardi and modern clinical data on nausea and vomiting in pregnancy. Exclusion criteria included irrelevant and non-scientific sources.

1. Review of Literature

Etymology and Definition

The term Chhardi refers to upward expulsion of gastric contents caused by vitiated Vata and Pitta doshas. When this occurs during pregnancy (Garbhavastha), it is termed Garbhini Chhardi. According to Charaka Samhita (Chikitsa Sthana 20/11), Chhardi arises when vitiated Vata propels Pitta and Kapha upward, leading to vomiting.

Classical References

- **Charaka Samhita** describes Garbhini Chhardi as a physiological manifestation in early gestation due to Garbha Vridhi and altered Agni, but pathological when excessive and causing dehydration or emaciation.
- **Sushruta Samhita** mentions that aggravated Pitta and Vata disturb the stomach and heart, causing nausea, loss of appetite, and repeated vomiting.
- **Kashyapa Samhita** emphasizes that improper diet, suppression of urges, and psychological stress aggravate doshas and lead to Chhardi in Garbhini.
- **Ashtanga Hridaya (Sharira Sthana 2/5)** states that Madhura, Sheeta, and Mridu substances pacify Pitta and are ideal for management.

Modern Correlation

In modern obstetrics, Garbhini Chhardi correlates with **nausea and vomiting of pregnancy (NVP)** or **hyperemesis gravidarum**. It usually occurs during the first trimester, associated with elevated human chorionic gonadotropin (hCG) and estrogen levels. Excessive vomiting can lead to electrolyte imbalance, dehydration, and weight loss.

2. Chikitsa (Treatment of Garbhini Chhardi)

Aims of Management

- To pacify aggravated Vata and Pitta doshas.
- To restore Agni (digestive fire).
- To prevent dehydration and nourish both mother and fetus.
- To ensure comfort and psychological stability of the mother.

Line of Treatment (Chikitsa Sutra)

1. Vata–Pitta Shamana
2. Agnideepana (digestive stimulation)
3. Garbhini Poshan (nourishment of mother and fetus)
4. Hridya & Stambhana dravya prayoga (use of heart-soothing, antiemetic herbs)

Ayurvedic Formulations and Remedies.

Formulation / Drug	Dose & Form	Indication / Action
Laja Manda (rice gruel)	Thin preparation with honey	Mild cases, pacifies Pitta, hydrates mother
Draksha Rasa / Avaleha	10–20 mL twice	Pitta Shamana,

	daily	antiemetic
Shatavari Ghrita	10 mL with warm milk	Strengthens uterus, improves appetite
Amalaki Churna with Sharkara	3–5 g twice daily	Raktapitta and Chhardi Shamana
Ksheerapaka of Musta, Parpataka, and Usheera	50–100 mL	Cooling, digestive, prevents nausea
Dhanyaka Siddha Jala (Coriander water)	sipped frequently	Mild Pitta-Vata pacification
Lauha Bhasma with Ghee and Sugar	125 mg twice daily	Corrects Agni and prevents anemia

Procedural Therapies

- Seka (gentle pouring of cold milk or sandalwood water on head) in severe Pitta aggravation.
- Abhyanga (gentle oil massage) and Snana (bathing) with cool decoctions for relaxation.
- Dhoomapana with mild herbs like Vacha and Haridra to reduce nausea.

Modern Supportive Measures

- Oral rehydration with electrolyte solution.
- Vitamin B6, doxylamine, and ginger supplements.
- Avoidance of strong odors, heavy meals, and stress.

3. Pathya–Apathya (Diet and Lifestyle in Garbhini Chhardi)

Pathya (Wholesome Regimen)

Ahara (Diet)

- Light, unctuous, and sweet-tasting foods like Manda, Yavagu, Ksheerapaka, Draksha, Kharjura, Ikshurasa, and Amalaki.
- Fresh cow's milk, ghee, and butter for nourishment.
- Small, frequent meals instead of large ones.
- Laja Manda prepared with sugar and milk as first-line diet.
- Warm water or Jeeraka siddha jala to sip throughout the day.
- Fruits like pomegranate, banana, and dates for strength.

Vihara (Lifestyle)

- Stay in a cool, calm, and ventilated environment.
- Adequate rest and avoidance of mental stress or anger.
- Light walks and Pranayama (breathing exercises).

- Listening to pleasant music and maintaining a peaceful mindset.

Apathya (Unwholesome Regimen)

Ahara (Dietary)

- Avoid sour, spicy, fermented, and fried foods.
- Avoid Viruddha Ahara (incompatible food combinations).
- Refrain from alcohol, caffeine, tobacco, and stale food.
- Avoid fasting or overeating.

Vihara (Lifestyle)

- Avoid late nights (Ratri Jagarana) and day sleep (Divaswapna).
- Avoid traveling, exposure to extreme heat, and excessive exertion.
- Avoid suppressing natural urges (urine, stool, vomiting).
- Avoid anxiety, grief, and excessive talking.

4. Clinical Significance

Following Pathya–Apathya and Vata–Pitta Shamana Chikitsa ensures Agni stability, improves digestion, prevents dehydration, and nurtures the fetus. The combined use of Laja Manda, Draksha Avaleha, and Shatavari Ghrita not only controls vomiting but also strengthens maternal health and supports fetal development.

DISCUSSION

According to Ayurveda, Garbhini Chhardi results from the imbalance of Vata and Pitta doshas during early pregnancy. Agni Mandya and Hridaya Kshobha lead to the upward expulsion of ingested food. The vitiated Pitta, mixed with Kapha, triggers vomiting. In modern science, hormonal alterations and gastric motility disturbances are considered primary causes.

Charaka recommends Laja Manda, Draksha Rasa, and Amalaki preparations to restore Agni and reduce Pitta. Sushruta suggests Madhura Dravyas and cooling regimens. Kashyapa advocates gentle, nourishing diets and avoidance of aggravating foods. These remedies balance Doshas, hydrate the body, and prevent recurrence. Pathya- Apathya plays a crucial role in management. Pathya (wholesome) includes sweet, unctuous, and easily digestible food such as milk, rice gruel, and ghee. Apathya (unwholesome) includes spicy, sour, and fermented foods, along with stress, irregular sleep, and suppression of natural urges. Modern studies support that Draksha and Amalaki have antioxidant and gastroprotective effects,

while Shatavari acts as an adaptogen, promoting hormonal balance. Thus, Ayurveda's recommendations align with modern understanding of gastrointestinal physiology and hormonal influences during pregnancy.

CONCLUSION

Garbhini Chhardi represents a physiological yet potentially pathological manifestation of pregnancy. Ayurveda offers preventive and curative measures that are safe and effective, emphasizing dosha harmony, proper diet, and lifestyle. Integrating Ayurvedic and modern perspectives can provide a comprehensive, patient-centered approach to managing hyperemesis gravidarum.

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